

1 *Article*

2 Shell Disorder Models Detect that Attenuated Omicron 3 has Harder Shells but is not a Descendant of the Wuhan 4 (SARS-CoV-2) Strain

5 Gerard Kian-Meng Goh ^{1,*}, A. Keith Dunker ², James A. Foster ^{3,4} and Vladimir N. Uversky ^{5,6}

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6 ¹ Goh's BioComputing, Singapore 548957. Republic of Singapore7 ² Center for Computational Biology, Indiana and Bioinformatics, Indiana University School of
8 Medicine, Indianapolis, Indiana 46202, USA; kedunker@iupui.edu9 ³ Department of Biological Sciences, University of Idaho, Moscow, Idaho 83844, USA;
10 foster@uidaho.edu11 ⁴ Institute for Bioinformatics and Evolutionary Studies, University of Idaho, Moscow, Idaho
12 83844, USA13 ⁵ Department of Molecular Medicine, Morsani College of Medicine, University of South Florida,
14 Tampa, Florida 33612, USA; vuffersky@health.usf.edu15 ⁶ Institute for Biological Instrumentation, Russian Academy of Sciences, Pushchino, Moscow
16 region, Russia17 * Correspondence: gohsbiocomputing@yahoo.com

18 **Abstract:** Before the SARS-CoV-2 Omicron variant emergence, Shell Disorder Models
19 (SDM) suggested that an attenuated precursor from pangolins may have entered
20 humans in 2017 or earlier. This was based on a shell-disorder analysis of SARS-CoV-1/2
21 and pangolin-Cov-2017. SDM suggests that Omicron is attenuated with almost identical
22 N (inner shell) disorder as pangolin-CoV-2017 (N-PID (percentage of intrinsic disorder):
23 44.8% vs. 44.9% - lower than other variants). The outer shell disorder (M-PID) of
24 Omicron is lower than that of other variants (5.4% vs. 5.9%). COVID-19-related CoVs
25 have the lowest M-PIDs (hardest outer-shell) among all CoVs. This is likely to be
26 responsible for higher contagiousness of SARS-CoV-2 and Omicron, since the hard
27 outer-shell protects the virion from salivary/mucosal anti-microbial enzymes.
28 Phylogenetic study using M reveals that Omicron branched off from an ancestor of the
29 Wuhan strain closely related to pangolin-CoVs. M, being evolutionarily conserved in
30 COVID-19, is most ideal for COVID-19 phylogenetic study. Omicron may have been
31 hiding among burrowing animals (e.g. pangolins) that provide optimal evolutionary
32 environments for attenuation and increase shell hardness, which is essential for fecal-
33 oral-respiratory transmission via buried feces. Incoming data support SDM showing the
34 presence of fewer infectious particles in the lungs than in the bronchi upon infection.

35 **Keywords:** coronavirus; COVID; intrinsic disorder; membrane; nucleocapsid;
36 nucleoprotein; Omicron; pangolin; shell; virulence

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1. Introduction

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1.1. COVID-19, SARS-CoV-2 and Omicron

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The coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) was first observed as an outbreak in Wuhan, China in December 2019. COVID-19 is known to be often fatal, and many patients need oxygen ventilators to assist with breathing [1]. After the outbreak in Wuhan, COVID-19 rapidly spread throughout China and the rest of the world. The virus responsible for COVID-19 was named SARS-CoV-2 (Severe Acute Respiratory Coronavirus 2), as it has about 79% genetic similarity to the 2003 SARS-CoV (SARS-CoV-1) [1-3]. A retrospective search among the archives for the close relatives of this virus yielded a genetic sequence from the RaTG13 sample of a beta-coronavirus isolated from bats found in Yunnan, China that has a 96% homology to SARS-CoV-2 [4-6]. Close relatives of SARS-CoV-2 were also found among Malayan pangolins: two sets of coronavirus (CoV) samples retrieved from the smuggled pangolins that were confiscated in Guangdong and Guangxi, China, during the years 2019 and 2017-18 respectively. They have an approximately 90% sequence identity with the SARS-CoV-2 [7-11].

Since the first outbreak in December 2019, many variants have overtaken the parent Wuhan strain. Many of these variants were identified by their differences in their spike (S) glycoprotein. The first variant that was regarded as a Variant of Concern (VOC) by WHO is the SARS-CoV-2 Alpha (B.1.1.7), which emerged in December 2020 and was 50% more contagious than the original Wuhan virus [12]. It differs from the Wuhan strain by the presence of three mutations in the S protein, N501Y, D614G, and P681H. There were several WHO-designated subsequent VOCs including Beta (B.135) and Gamma (P1) variants. The most troublesome variants at the time of writing of this manuscript are the Delta (B.1.1.617.2) and Omicron (B.1.1.529). Delta was first found in India around May 2020 and spread quickly around the world. It was found to be 50% more contagious than the Alpha variant and has several mutations not seen in previous variants, such as L452R, T478K and P681R. Omicron came later with the first detection by South African physicians in November 2021 [1,12-14]. This heavily mutated variant was found to be less severe than previous variants but about twice as infectious as Delta. There is, however, something else that is strange about the Omicron. Many of the 50 mutations found in Omicron were never seen before in previous variants [15]. This basically implies that this variant had been hiding somewhere for much of the pandemic. In fact, phylogenetic studies using S have traced the lineage to the Wuhan strain dating back to February 2020 [15]. Our study will provide evidence that Omicron did not emerge as a descendant of the Wuhan strain but, rather, from an ancestor of the Wuhan virus that is closer to pangolin CoVs.

The result, as we will see, arose from a phylogenetic study using M protein, a part of the CoV outer shell. A strange characteristic pertaining to the COVID-19 M proteins was first detected in a study during the pandemic using the Shell Disorder Models (SDMs) [16-18]. It was discovered that among CoVs, all COVID-19-related viruses have the relatively hard outer shells. The hard outer shell or low M-PID (Percentage of Intrinsic Disorder) is associated with higher resistance of a virus to harsh conditions, which, in turn, reflects the mode of viral transmission. Hard shell disorder can be found in viruses infecting burrowing animals even if they are distantly related, as their fecal-oral transmission of CoVs is likely to involve contacts with feces that have been buried for a long time [17,18].

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1.2. The three closely Shell Disorder Models

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The SDMs that were used to study CoVs consist of three closely related models [16,17,19-25]. The parent "Viral Shape Shifter" model was built based on the observation that a large number of HIV-1 variants have unusually high disorder levels in the outer shell (matrix) that are not commonly found among viruses [16,17,21,24-26]. This characteristic is believed to be associated with sexual transmission of viruses and the failure to find an effective vaccine for HIV, HCV, and HSV [16,21,27,28]. A daughter model was developed in 2012,

when we published the transmission- shell disorder model, in which correlations between modes of transmission and shell disorder were described [23]. Starting from 2015, a series of publications provided the groundwork for a third model, the Virulence-Inner Shell Disorder Model [16,19-22]. In this model, a strong relationships were found between the virulence and inner shell disorder for a variety of viruses, such as Ebola virus, Nipah virus, Zika virus, and Dengue virus.

1.3. The Shell Disorder Models as applied to SARS-CoV-2

By the time genetic information became available in the early stages of the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic, the SDMs were readily deployed to understand the nature of this new and dangerous virus. The SDMs use Artificial Intelligence (AI) to inspect the sequence of proteins and to predict disordered residues [29-32]. The PID provides a gauge for the level of disorder for a protein. According to the Transmission-Shell Disorder Model, SARS-CoV-2 fell into the same category as SARS-CoV-1 (2003 SARS-CoV), which has intermediate levels of both fecal-oral and respiratory transmission potentials [23]. This analysis was based mainly on the intermediate level of N-PID (i.e., inner shell protein), but there is something else very odd about SARS-CoV-2, not seen in SARS-CoV-1 and for that matter, most members of the CoV family. The outer shell (M) of SARS-CoV-1 is one of the hardest known, which is characterized by its low M-PID [17,18,33]. Upon seeing this, we knew it had something to do with the contagiousness of the virus. More specifically, the hardness of M provides greater virion protection against the anti-microbial enzymes found in the mucus and saliva . The hard M protein is conserved throughout all COVID-19 related viruses including pangolin-CoVs [17,18,33].

1.4. Solving the Omicron mysteries using Shell Disorder Models

With the emergence of Omicron as the current dominant SARS-CoV-2 strain, there are still many mysteries surrounding this variant as aforementioned. Where did the Omicron come from? Where was it hiding [15]? The SDMs might have specific answers to these questions. They have detected that the Omicron M is harder than M of any of the previous variants. The phylogenetic tree using M indicates that Omicron is a descendant of the Wuhan virus but, rather, arose from an ancestor of the Wuhan virus that is closer to the 2019 pangolin CoV. What is also stranger is that before the emergence of Omicron, the SDMs suggested that a precursor to the SARS-CoV-2 entered the humans in 2017 or before as an attenuated strain [17,18]. This analysis was based mainly on the N-PID. When Omicron emerged, it was quickly determined clinically and experimentally to be milder than previous variants [13,14,34,35]. We found that the N-PIDs of both the pangolin-CoV 2017 and Omicron to be nearly identical. This basically means that the Virulence-Inner Shell Disorder Model correctly predicted the attenuated nature of Omicron even before its actual emergence. We shall discuss the implications and evidence of these in greater details.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Viral Shells

An important concept used in the SDMs is protein intrinsic disorder, which is defined as lack of unique structure in the entire proteins or protein regions with specific biological functions [36-42]. Since there are several noticeable differences between the amino acid sequences of ordered and disordered proteins, multiple computational tools have been developed to recognize regions of disorder. One of such tool is PONDR® VLXT, which uses neural network (artificial intelligence (AI)) trained using known ordered and disordered sequences to predict residues that are disordered [29-31]. PONDR® VLXT is known to be highly sensitive to local sequence peculiarities and can efficiently find protein-protein interactions [43,44], which make it suitable for the study of viral shell proteins, which are often ordered as a result of protein-protein complex formation. In fact, in the past, this algorithm has been successfully used to study a wide variety of viruses including HIV, Dengue viruses (DENV), Ebola virus (EBOV), Nipah virus, and SARS-CoV-1/2 [16-27,33,45-48]. PONDR-VLXT is freely available online (www.pondr.com).

The necessary protein sequences were retrieved from either UniProt or NCBI-Protein/ GenBank (<https://www.uniprot.org/>) or

160 <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/protein>, respectively). The obtained sequences
 161 were fed into the PONDR® VLXT neural network. The resulting information
 162 and sequences were stored in a relational database using JAVA
 163 (<http://www.java.com>) and MYSQL (<https://www.mysql.com>). The PONDR®
 164 VLXT scores were also imported into OpenOffice spreadsheet (
 165 <https://www.openoffice.org>), and the PONDR® VLXT plots were created. The
 166 sequences downloaded were input into the NCBI BLASTP
 167 (<https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi?PAGE=Proteins>). The graphical
 168 sequence comparison was used to study the sequence differences and was
 169 graphically adapted using GIMP (<https://www.gimp.org>). The sequence
 170 similarity percentages were carefully noted and used as part of our analysis.
 171 Multivariate analyses were computed using R package [49] and the respective
 172 r (correlation) coefficients were recorded. Illustrations were drawn using both
 173 GIMP and OpenOffice.

174 The N and M sequences from a variety of CoVs were first uploaded
 175 separately onto EMBI-EBI website
 176 (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/Tools/msa/clustalo/>). This CLUSTAL Omega
 177 software allows the generation of phylogenetic trees using M and N
 178 respectively. The M sequences of COVID-19-related viruses were then
 179 uploaded into another website TREX ([http://www.trex.uqam.ca/index.php?](http://www.trex.uqam.ca/index.php?action=align&project=trex)
 180 [action=align&project=trex](http://www.trex.uqam.ca/index.php?action=align&project=trex)), that uses CLUSTALW to generate a phylogenetic
 181 tree using M with distance correction, unlike the trees generated by CLUSTAL
 182 OMEGA. The phylogenetic trees were enhanced and annotated using GIMP
 183 and used as part of the results.

184 3. Results

185 3.1. Modes of Transmission- Shell Disorder Model

186 The Mode of Transmission-Shell Disorder Model was developed 10 years
 187 ago with its first publication in 2012 [23]. The model categorized CoVs into
 188 three groups using M- and N-PIDs. Group A included CoVs with higher levels
 189 of respiratory but lower levels of fecal-oral transmission, group B contained
 190 viruses those with the intermediate potentials for both fecal-oral and
 191 respiratory transmissions, whereas group C encompassed CoVs with higher
 192 fecal-oral transmission potential and lower levels of respiratory transmission.
 193 When the initial paper was published in 2012 just before the emergence of
 194 the Middle Eastern Respiratory Syndrome (MERS), SARS-CoV-1 was found to be
 195 in group B [23], which consists of the CoVs with the intermediate respiratory
 196 and fecal-oral transmission potentials, since in SARS-CoV-1, the N- and M-
 197 PIDs were evaluated at 50% and 9%, respectively. When the MERS-CoV
 198 sequence became available after the outbreak, it became clear that MERS-CoV
 199 fell into group C (lower respiratory higher fecal-oral transmission, given that
 200 MERS-CoV N- and M-PIDs were 43% and 10%, respectively as seen in **Table 1**
 201 [46]. The greater fecal-oral transmission potential behavior of MERS-CoV was
 202 actually observed [16], thereby validating the model.

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209 **Table 1.** Categorization of CoVs by N- and M-PIDs to predict levels of the respiratory
 210 and fecal-oral transmission ($p < 0.001$, $r = 0.8$). The original model involved
 211 categorization mainly by N-PID, and group D was not included. The updated model
 212 integrates new knowledge arising from SARS-CoV-2 and Omicron.

Coronavirus	M-PID	UniProt(U) Genbank(G)	N-PID	UniProt(U) Genbank(G)	Group/Remarks
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		Accession Code (M Proteins) ^a		Accession Code (N) ^a		
HCoV-229E	23	P15422	56	P15130		Group A
IBV(Avian) ^c	10	P69606	56	Q8JMI6		Higher levels of respiratory transmission lower levels of fecal-oral transmission
Bovine	7.8	P69704	53.1	Q8V432(U)		Group B
PEDV (Porcine) ^c	8	P59771(U)	51.7	Q07499(U)		Intermediate levels of respiratory and fecal- oral transmission
Canine (Resp.)	7	A3E2F6(U)	50.5	A3E2F7(U)		
HCoV-OC43	7	Q4VID2(U)	51	P33469(U)		
SARS-CoV-1	8.6	P59596(U)	50.2	P59595(U)		
HCoV-NL63	11	Q6Q1R9(U)	49	Q6Q1R8(U)		
Bats ^b	11.2±5.3	A3EXD6(U)	47.7±0.9	Q3LZX4(U)		
MHV(Murine) ^c	8	Q9JEB4(U)	46.8	P03416(U)		Group C
MERS-CoV	9.1	K0BU37(U)	44.7	K0BVN3(U)		Lower levels of respiratory transmission higher levels of fecal-oral transmission
TGEV(Porcine) ^c	14	P09175(U)	44.3	P04134(U)		
Canine (Ent.)	8	B8RIR2(U)	42.41	Q04700(U)		
HCoV-HKU1 ^d	4.5	Q14EA7(U)	40	Q0ZME3(U)		
			37.4			
SARS-CoV-2						Group D
[Wuhan]	5.9	YP009724393(G)	48.2	YP009724397(G)		High Respiratory and Fecal-oral Transmission Potentials
[Delta]	5.9	QUX81285(G)	47.1±0.5	QYM89845(G)		
[Omicron]	5.4	UFO59282(G)	44.8	UFO692871(G)		
Pangolin-CoV ^e	5.6±0.9	QIA428617(G)	46.6±1.6	QIA48630(G)		
Rabbit-CoV	5.7	H9AA37(U)	52.2 6 ^e	H9AA59(U)		
RaTG13	4.1	QHT63303(G)	48.5	QHR63308(G)		

^a UniProt (U): [<https://www.uniprot.org/>]; GenBank-NCBI (G): [<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/protein>]

^b Summary figures on bats. Further details on the bat samples can be found in **Table 2**. 4 out of 5 bat-CoVs are in group B. High standard deviations are seen for N- and M-PIDs as denoted by "±"

^c MHV(murine hepatitis virus), IBV (infectious bronchitis virus), PEDV (porcine epidemic diarrhea virus, TGEV(Transmissible, gastroenteritis virus).

^d HCoV-HKU1 has one of the lowest M PID, which could qualify it for group D but its N PID is also abnormally low. Much is still not understood about HCoV-HKU1 [50,51]. For these reasons, HCoV-HKU1 is left in group C.

^e Details on the existing pangolin-CoVs known can be found in **Table 2**. Standard deviation is denoted by "±".

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Figure 1. A. All CoV are closely related to SARS-CoV-2 (**).SARS-CoV-2 has the lowest M-PID (hardest Outer Shell) among all the CoV analyzed in this study. **B.** A hard outer shell is seen among COVID-related CoVs. Omicron (XX) has the lowest among all SARS-CoV=2 variants.

3.2. Hardest outer shell (lowest M-PIDs) is seen in all COVID-related CoVs: Burrowing animals

Yet another chance to validate the model came with the COVID-19 pandemic. This time, SARS-CoV-2 (Wuhan strain) had to be place in group B alongside with SARS-CoV-1 [33]. While it does seem to validate the model, something that is very strange was also seen. SARS-CoV-2 has one of the hardest outer shells in its entire CoV family (**Figure 1**) [33,48]. One exception is the rabbit-CoV, which is not closely related to SARS-CoV-2. Both rabbits and pangolins are burrowing animals [17,18]. Pangolin CoVs have comparatively hard M and were found to be closely related to SARS-CoV-2 [17,18].

3.3. High infectivity of SARS-CoV-2 is related to its abnormally hard outer shell (lowest M-PIDs)

The original model was designed using knowledge of CoVs from farm animals, especially those of porcine. Strong correlations between the transmission mode and, especially, N-PID were observed ($r^2 = 0.77$). A minute but statistically significantly greater correlation could be found when M-PID was added as an additional independent variable ($r^2 = 0.83$). Biologically, inner shell proteins are known to assist the replication and disorder in the inner shell does enhance the replication [52]. It is for this reason, the correlations between virulence and inner shell disorder have been detected in a sister shell disorder model [19-22]. Similarly, greater disorder of the N protein allows greater copies to be present in vital organs, mucus, and saliva (saliva and mucus are more complicated as we will see). N disorder is therefore correlated with the mode of transmission potentials because of a minimal amount of infectious particles need to be present in the saliva and mucus before a virus can be transmissible by the respiratory modes [33].

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M protein, however, is more enigmatic. Some viruses that have high fecal-oral transmission potentials do not need to remain in the environment for a long time, since fecal-oral transmission is often very efficient in farm animal, such as pigs, as in the case of the TGEV. It is for this reason that TGEV M-PID is somewhat high, at about 14%. While the slight correlation between M-PID and mode of transmission was detected, the exact nature of this relationship was impossible to understand, because there were very few CoVs with extremely low M-PIDs as seen in **Figure 1A** [23,33,46]. The COVID-19 pandemic is actually an event that sheds light on the role of M in transmissibility. The unusually hard outer shell (low M-PID) can be seen among all of the SARS-CoV-2 close relatives, as shown in **Figure 1** and **Table 2**. The high infectivity of SARS-CoV-2 is likely the result of its hard M protein protecting the virion from damage arising from the anti-microbial enzymes found in mucus and saliva [33,53,54]. In fact, hard outer shells are often found in other viruses that are commonly found in the saliva, such as rabies and DENV, which is exposed to mosquito saliva [20,26].

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Table 2. Details of the pangolin CoVs and Bat CoVs N/M PIDs and their sequence similarities with the SARS-CoV and SARS-CoV-2 as references. Using N-PID, the SDMs have detected two sub-variants of Delta not previously detected (Delta1, Delta2)

Coronavirus	Sequence Similarity M (%)	M PID (%)	Accession: UniProt(U) GenBank(G)	Sequence Similarity N (%)	N PID (%)	Accession UniProt(U) GenBank(G)
SARS-CoV-1	90.5	8.6	P59596(U)	90.5	50.2	P59595(U)
Civet-SARS-CoV	90.1	8.6	Q3ZTE9(U)	90.01	49.1	Q3ZTE4(U)
Pangolin-CoV		5.6±0.9			46.6±1.6 ^a	
2019	98.2	^a	QIG55948(G)	98	48.7	QIG55953(G)
2018	97.7	6.3	QIQ54051(G)	93.8	46.3	QIQ54056(G)
2017***	98.2	4.5	QIA48617(G)	94	44.9	QIA48630(G)
		5.9		93.32	46.5	QIA48656(G)
SARS-CoV-2						
[Wuhan]	100	5.9	YP009724393(G)	100	48.2	YP009724397(G)
[Delta1]	99.1	5.9	QUX81285(G)	99.3	46.8	QYM89997(G)
[Delta2]	99.1	5.9	QUX81285(G)	99.1	47.5	QYM89845(G)
[Omicron]**	98.7	5.4	UFO59282(G)	98.6	44.8	UFO692871(G)
Bat-CoV		11.2±1	Q9JEB4		47.7±0.9 ^a	
		^{5a}				
RATG13	99.6	4.1	QHR63303(G)	99.1	48.5	QHR63308(G)
Bat 512	35.5	15.3	Q0Q463(U)	29.4	46.5	Q0Q462(U)
HKU3	91	7.7	Q3LZX9(U)	89.6	48	Q3LZX4(U)
HKU4	42.7	16.4	A3EXA0(U)	51.1	48.5	A3EXA1(U)
HKU5	44.7	11.8	A3EXD6(U)	47.9	47.1	A3EXD7(U)

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^a Standard deviation is denoted by "±".

*** Attenuated strains detected

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The emergence of the Omicron variant does not only provide even more proof of the role of M, but also highlights the close relationship of a harder M to transmissibility. Omicron is more infectious than the original Wuhan virus, or, for that matter, all previous SARS-CoV-2 variants, and it is also more infectious and has a harder M (M-PID, 5.4%) than previous variants including the Wuhan strain (M-PID, 5.9%) as seen in **Tables 1-2** and **Figure 1**. While we believe that the original Transmission-Shell Disorder Model is valid as a tool to gain insight to the evolution of CoVs, SARS-CoV-2 variants and, particularly, Omicron, have hinted that the model may not be complete, as the original model was designed without sufficient samples of CoVs with low M-PIDs. CoVs with extremely low M-PIDs should be categorized as a totally different

group; i.e., group D, which consists of viruses with high fecal-oral and respiratory transmission, as seen in **Table 1**. This added feature is still able to maintain a good correlation ($r^2 = 0.7$, $p < 0.05$).

Tables 1 and 2 show that the M- and N-PIDs of Omicron (M-PID: 5.4%, N-PID: 44.8%) are different from those of Delta (M-PID: 5.9%, N-PID: 47.1±0.5%) or Wuhan (M-PID: 5.9%, N-PID: 48.2%). While we have explained the significance of a lower M-PID, the disorder status of N tells a different story and is subjected to the scrutiny using the Virulence-Inner Shell Disorder Model. The model is best summarized by **Figure 2A**. As in the case of Ebola virus, there is a correlation between the level of disorder of the inner shell protein and virulence [22]. As aforementioned, this correlation has been found in a variety of viruses, such as EBOV, DENV, and NiV [19-22]. The reason that the inner shell disorder is correlated with virulence has to do with the fact that the inner shell of viruses usually play important roles in replication. As a result, the higher disorder of the proteins in the inner shell provides means for more efficient viral replications. Protein intrinsic disorder defines partner pliability and determines better fits in protein-protein/DNA/RNA/lipid interactions [52,55-78]. Viruses often use the strategy of "Trojan Horse" for immune evasion [16,27,47,79], in which the virus would replicate very rapidly before the host immune system can detect its presence. This strategy can be deployed using greater disorder at the level of inner shell proteins. This strategy often, however, backfires on the virus by overwhelming vital organs with a large amount of virus copies and thereby killing the host.

3.4. The SDMs suggest that an attenuated precursor from pangolins enter humans in 2017 or before: Omicron resembles Pangolin-CoV 2017 with lower M-PID

Evidence that the Virulence-Inner Shell Disorder Model is applicable to the SARS-CoV-1 and SARS-CoV-2 can be found in **Figure 2B**, showing a reasonably good correlation ($r = 0.8$, $p < 0.05$) between the case fatality rate (CFR) and N-PID. The CFRs of the various SARS-CoV-2 are estimated extrapolations [80] even if it is certain that the CFR of Omicron (0.16) [81] is certainly much lower than that of the other variants [81]. There is no evidence that the death rate of Delta is higher than that of the Wuhan strain. The CFR estimates of the Wuhan strain range from 0.5-2% [80] depending on the investigation but is definitely considered much higher than that of Omicron [3,14,81]. SARS-CoV-1 has a CFR of about 10% [3], which is definitely well above that of the SARS-CoV-2.

We will note that the Virulence-Inner Shell Disorder Model is predicting that Omicron and Pangolin-CoVs (especially the pangolin-CoV 2017), are attenuated. Before the emergence of the Omicron and upon the analysis of the pangolin CoVs, SARS-CoV-1, and SARS-CoV-2, the SDMs suggested that a precursor from pangolin-CoV may have entered humans and spread silently, as early as 2017 or before as an attenuated virus before becoming more virulent.

Figure 2. The Virulence-Inner Shell Disorder Model. **A.** Correlation of the Ebola (EBOV) virulence and inner shell (NP) disorder ($r=0.95$, $p<0.05$) [22]. **B.** Correlation between the SARS virulence and the inner shell (N) disorder ($r=0.8$, $p<0.05$). Abbreviations: Pangolin-CoV 2017-2019 (Pang2017-Pang2019). SARS-CoV-1 (SARS1), Wuhan (Wuhan strain), Reston EBOV (REBOV), Bundibugyo (BEBOV), Sudan (SEBOV), Zaire (ZEBOV), Marburg virus (MARV).

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This hypothesis was based mainly on the analysis of the N-PIDs. Upon the Omicron emergence, it was quickly determined that this lineage is milder than the other SARS-CoV-2 variants. Within the frames of the typical SDM reproducibility, the N-PIDs of Omicron (44.8%) and pangolin CoV 2017 (44.9%) are almost identical (see below and **Tables 1-2**). There was an assumption that the spread of the attenuated precursor could involve a slower spread, but this was based on the hypothesis that the M-PID of the precursor was the same as the M-PID of SARS-CoV-2 or higher. The pangolin CoV 2017 has the same M-PID as SARS-CoV-2, but Omicron has a lower M-PID (5.4%), which could account for its greater infectivity.

3.5. N Disorder Patterns: Pangolin CoV and Omicron and Wuhan SARS-CoV-2 strain

Since PONDR® VLXT is dependent on the protein sequence for its prediction, it is necessary to examine the sequence and disorder comparatively. **Figure 3** shows the PONDR plots for N. **Figure 3A** represents a comparison of the PONDR plots of the N protein of the Wuhan and pangolins strains, whereas **Figure 3B** compares the Wuhan and the Omicron. While it has already been seen that Omicron N-PID (44.7%) resembles that of Pangolin CoV 2017 (44.8%) (see **Figure 2B** and **Table 2**), **Figure 3** shows that the PONDR plots of the Pangolin CoV and Omicron resemble each other, when compared to the Wuhan strain. Within the disordered N-terminal domains, the regions of local order are found around residues 12-23 of both Pangolin CoV and Omicron, but

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368 Comparison between the Wuhan strain and pangolin CoV 2017. C. Sequence and
369 disorder comparison of N proteins from the Wuhan strain and Omicron variant.
370 Abbreviations: N-terminus RNA-Binding Domain (NTD RNA-Binding), Nuclear
371 Localization Signal (NLS) [82]

372 3.6. Disorder differences near the NTD RNA-binding region

373 Another noticeable difference in the disorder profiles can be found in
374 **Figure 3A**, where there is a dissimilarity around locations 212-215, with the
375 ordered region starting at 212 and 215 for the Omicron variant and Wuhan
376 strain (**Figure 3C**). This difference can be traced to both the differences in
377 location in location as the result of the deletion at locations 31-33 and the
378 mutations at R203K and G204R. Mutations around this region have been
379 observed to induce virulence presumably by enhancing viral replication. It
380 should be noted that deletion of the polar residues and mutations to less polar
381 residues are often related to the induction of some local order [30,32,83-87],
382 which is mostly the case for Omicron. It can be seen that most of the mutations
383 leading to lesser disorder in Omicron and pangolin CoVs are located close to or
384 within the NTD RNA-binding domain [82], which implies that the attenuation
385 emerged from the inability of the two attenuated viruses to bind to the viral
386 RNA more efficiently during the replication process.

387 3.7. The phylogenetic tree using M provides the greatest accuracy as it is 388 evolutionarily conserved and recombinations can confuse previous phylogenetic studies

389 We have argued in previous papers that phylogenetic studies offer that
390 best study as all viruses closely related to SARS-CoV-2 have the hardest outer
391 shell among its CoV family. A glimpse at the sequence identities especially
392 COVID-19-related viruses brings us to the attention that the M proteins are
393 among the most conserved proteins among COVID-19-related viruses. The
394 evolutionary necessity of a hard outer shell can be found in their relationship
395 with the burrowing pangolins and their fecal-oral-respiratory transmission via
396 buried feces. This can be confirmed by data summarized in **Table 2** with its
397 high sequence similarities among all the COVID-19-related viruses.
398 Furthermore, reported studies argued that the use of a protein that is not
399 conserved among strains and variants could lead to the mistake, as
400 recombination could have happened, and current phylogenetic algorithms
401 handle recombination very poorly that could lead to giving the wrong results
402 [88].

403 3.8. The phylogenetic tree using M suggests that Omicron did not arise from the 404 Wuhan strain but from one of its ancestors that are closer to pangolin CoVs

405 The difference between phylogenetic trees of M and N can be found in
406 **Figure 4**. As already seen in our previous studies, the phylogenetic tree using
407 M clusters the pangolin CoVs near SARS-CoV-2 unlike those using other
408 proteins or building a phylogenetic tree based on the genome-wide analysis.
409 With Omicron, it yields further interesting and peculiar results. The
410 phylogenetic tree using N (**Figure 4A**) tells us that Omicron probably split
411 from the Wuhan strain just as Delta and the other variants did. An examination
412 of **Figure 4A** reveals that the split came in earlier than that of Delta. This result
413 is similar to the phylogenetic tree using S1 that tells us that Omicron, unlike
414 other SARS-CoV-2 variants, split off from the Wuhan strain within 1-3 months
415 upon the initial Wuhan outbreak. The phylogenetic tree using N seen in **Figure**
416 **4B** seems to be consistent with the phylogenetic tree using S1. The
417 phylogenetic trees based M as seen in **Figures 4A** and **4C** are saying something
418 else that is strangely different. This analysis suggested that Omicron did not
419 descend from the Wuhan strain, but rather originates from one of its ancestral
420 strain. This is more clearly seen in **Figure 4C**, showing that the Omicron is
421 closer to the pangolin CoVs than to the Wuhan virus or any other SARS-CoV-2
422 variants. This immediately raises many questions, which we will address later.

423 We also argue that the phylogenetic tree using M is the most accurate way
424 of evolutionary analysis, as M is the most conserved as seen in the consistently
425 low M-PIDs among all COVID-19-related CoVs (**Figure 4C**), and there are high
426 similarity levels among close relatives of SARS-CoV-2 (**Table 2**). Being
427 conserved means that there is lower likelihood of a recombination taking place
428 for the protein and current phylogenetic algorithms handle such recombination
429 poorly [88].

Figure 4. The Phylogenetic trees using M and N proteins. **A.** Phylogenetic tree using M protein. **B.** Phylogenetic tree using N protein. **C.** Phylogenetic tree using M protein for COVID-19-related variants and strains showing Omicron to be an entirely different branch from the other SARS-CoV-2 variants, being closer to pangolin CoVs. (Additional NCBI accession codes for M proteins: QXY06216 (Alpha), QWA53378 (Beta), and QWW7597 (Gamma)). The phylogenetic tree in C includes distance correction, unlike those in A and B.

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Figure 4C shows that the story remains consistent even if the other VOCs were added (Alpha, Beta, and Gamma). We may noticed that the M-PIDs (5.9%) of Alpha, Beta and Gamma are identical to those of Delta variant and Wuhan strain. Omicron stands out alone at 5.4%. This has implications on the infectivity of Omicron as a harder outer shell will enable the virus to shed more particles nasally and orally as it will be more protected against the antimicrobial enzymes found in the saliva and mucus. How did Omicron manage to get these unique characteristics? We will discuss this later in more details.

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Figure 5. Zoonotic relationships of SARS-CoV-1/2. SARS-CoV-1 (SARS1) was likely in an intermediary host (palm civet cat) for a relatively short period, which could account for its high virulence. SARS-CoV-2, (SARS2) on the other hand, could have been in pangolins for a long period of time and thus first entered as an attenuated strain. Omicron had the opportunity to retain its attenuation by a reverse zoonotic transfer back to a burrowing animal (in blue).

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3.9. Omicron may have been the result of a reverse zoonotic transfer from humans back to a burrowing animal

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We have been able to see in **Figures 4A** and **4C** that pangolin CoVs cluster around SARS-CoV-2, making pangolin CoVs the closest relatives to SARS-CoV-2. **Figure 5** summarizes the likely relationship that the SARS-CoV-1 and SARS-CoV-2 have with humans, bats, and civet cat/pangolins. **Figure 5A** shows the relationship between bat, virus and civet cat. A bat version of SARS-CoV-1 had crossed into the palm civet cat and not long after that the civet cat virus enter the human population through human contacts with civet cats. This took place in a relatively short period of time compared to SARS-CoV-2 in **Figure 5**. This prolonged virus-human interactions may have been assisted and preceded by a similarly prolonged period of interactions between the virus and pangolin. As for Omicron, it could have been assisted by a reverse zoonotic viral transfer from human back to pangolins or a similar burrowing animal as illustrated in the area shaded blue in **Figure 5**. It should also be noted that bats often cohabits with pangolins in burrows, which may provide an ideal environment for the exchange of viruses [89].

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3.10. Life-cycles

In our previous studies, we have shown that the life-cycles of SARS-CoV-2 variants are different from that of the SARS-CoV-1. The lower disorder in N protein contributes to the lesser amounts of infectious particles produced in vital organs in contrast to the N of SARS-CoV-1. The abnormally low M disorder found in all COVID-19 CoVs protects the particles from the harsh

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anti-microbial enzymes and thus allowing heavy nasal and oral shedding [17,18,33]. The S protein does affect the life-cycle in different ways. The S protein of SARS-CoV-2 contains a polybasic furin cleavage site not found in SARS-CoV-1, pangolin-CoVs or RaTG13 that assists in the more efficient viral entry [2,18,90]. It is for this reason experimental studies have shown that SARS-CoV-2 produces more intracellular RNA than SARS-CoV-1, whereas SARS-CoV-1 produces more infectious particles than SARS-CoV-2 [91,92]. These differences are summarized in **Figure 6**, where we can see two viral particles entering the Wuhan strain and Omicron variant as opposed to the single particle in SARS-CoV-1 (SARS1). The life-cycle lengths of the Wuhan strain and Omicron variant are also longer than that of SARS-CoV-1. Clinical studies have shown that SARS-CoV-2 sheds larger amounts of particles from the beginning when the patients show the first sign of its symptoms until right to the end with many patients still being infectious even after the symptoms are gone [92,93]. In the case of SARS-CoV-1, shedding begins late and lasts only for a while. Omicron has a different life-cycle from the Wuhan strain showing its symptoms very quickly [13,14]. All these are likely arising from the differences in the S protein-protein interactions.

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Figure 6. The life-cycles of the SARS-CoV-1/2, SARS-CoV-1 (SARS1) produces more infectious particles especially in vital organs arising from the differences in N PIDs but sheds lesser infectious particles orally and nasally because its outer shell (M) is not as hard and protective as SARS-CoV-2. SARS1 and SARS-CoV-2 have different life-cycles as a result of their difference in the S proteins. This is denoted by the differences in the lengths of their life-cycles and the number of particles at viral entry. Note: Numbers of infectious particles shown are comparative and qualitative illustrations, not to meant to be exact quantifications.

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4. Discussion

4.1. The shell disorder approach to solve the mysteries of Omicron

We have seen that the SDMs have provided evidence that Omicron is of a specific and peculiar nature in terms of evolution. The Virulence-Inner Shell Disorder Model has identified it to be attenuated based on the Omicron low N-PID of 44.8%. In a previous study, the model had identified the 2017 pangolin CoV or a similar strain to be a potential attenuated precursor to the SARS-CoV-2 that could be spreading before the pandemic [17]. The 2017 pangolin CoV has an N-PID of 44.9%, which is very close to Omicron.

As for the greater infectivity of Omicron, the Transmission-Shell Disorder Model points to its low M-PID that lower than that of all the SARS-CoV-2 variants including the Wuhan. strain Just as SARS-CoV-2 is more contagious than SARS-CoV-1 due to their difference in M-PIDs, the same can be said of Omicron and the rest of the variants (**Tables 1-2, Figure 4C**). The hard outer shell (low M-PID) facilitates greater protection against the anti-microbial enzymes found in the mucus and saliva [53,54]. As a result, the virus is able to shed large amounts of particles orally and nasally without overwhelming vital organs with higher viral loads.

4.2. Where was Omicron hiding all these years? According to the Shell Disorder Models: Among Within a specific specie of burrowing animals

Upon the discovery of Omicron by a group of South African doctors, the variant was shrouded in complete mystery, and even today, despite the emergence of the results from clinical, experiment and computational studies, many aspects of the Omicron mystery remain unanswered. For instance, it was believed that Omicron diverged from the Wuhan strain before all known variants but it remains a mystery as to where it was hiding all along, as there has been no genetic trace ever detected before [15]. One suggestion was that it had been hiding in an immunocompromised individual, e.g., an HIV patient. It was discovered that SARS-CoV-2 remained in the HIV-positive patients for many months [94]. Another possibility is that the virus had been hiding in another animal, such as mice [95].

In this paper, a different approach is used to look at the Omicron. The SDMs point that the phylogenetic tree using M is the best possible phylogenetic approach, as the models had found M to be the most conserved among all COVID-19-related viruses. The M phylogenetic tree concurs with the S1 phylogenetic tree in the sense that we see an Omicron divergence from a parent lineage at an early stage unlike the other variants. As for where Omicron was hiding, the SDMs have some specific answers. As we see in the M phylogenetic trees in **Figures 4B and 4C**, the closest relatives of SARS-CoV-2 are pangolin CoVs, as pangolin CoVs might provide an evolutionary environment suitable for the maintenance of hard outer shell (low M-PID) arising from the habits of pangolins. Not only does the SDMs suggest that SARS-CoV-2 arose from pangolin CoVs, it is likely that the virus has been moving to and fro between humans and pangolin CoVs as highlighted in blue (**Figure 5**). In fact, **Figures 4B and 4C** tell us that the pangolin CoVs are probably the closest relatives of Omicron.

As for hiding in the body of an immunocompromised individual [94], the fact that the M-PID of Omicron is lower than M-PIDs of all other SARS-CoV-2 variants seems to provide evidence that hiding in an immunocompromised patient may not have happened, as it is difficult to envision that a harder outer shell would provide any evolutionary advantage in the body of such individual. On the other hand, a lower M disorder does provide definite advantages in the body and buried feces of a burrowing animal as it helps facilitate fecal-oral-respiratory transmission as the virus needs to remain intact in buried feces for a long time before infecting the next host. The suggestion that the virus was hiding in mice as mentioned in several studies [95], is, however, complex. Mice have two competing evolutionary pressures. Mice in the wild live in burrows, whereas, those in urban settings and villages live in houses with humans [96]. Mice have evolved with humans for centuries. This complexity is also captured in our data on disorder analysis. While MHV (murine hepatitis virus) has a somewhat high M-PID of 8%, the closely related HCoV-HKU1 has one of the lowest M-PID values (4.2%) known (**Table 1**). There is still a shroud of mystery surrounding HCoV-HKU1 even if we know

568 that it is closely related to MHV. We still have absolutely no knowledge on
569 how or when the virus entered humans [50,51].

570 4.3. *Omicron like pangolin-CoV 2017, is inherently attenuated*

571 From the beginning, physicians in South African had observed that most
572 Omicron patients had mild symptoms and did not require hospitalization or
573 oxygen ventilators, unlike previous outbreaks. As more data rolled in from
574 South Africa and the rest of the world, the milder nature of Omicron was
575 confirmed to be true [12-14,34,35]. Furthermore, experimental studies done by
576 various laboratories throughout the world using tissues or animal models have
577 demonstrated that more viral particles can be found in nasal and bronchial
578 tissues than those of lungs [34,35].

579 As we have seen, the Virulence-Inner Disorder Model did predict the
580 Omicron attenuation. In fact, we also suggested in previous studies that
581 pangolin CoVs may have quietly entered the human population around 2017
582 or before as an attenuated precursor of SARS-CoV-2. The prediction was based
583 on the assumption that the precursor was something very similar to the 2017
584 pangolin CoV, which has M- and N-PIDs of 5.8% and 44.9% (Table 2). As
585 aforementioned, we may notice that its N-PID is very similar to that of
586 Omicron (44.8%), which implies that the SDMs have actually predicted
587 Omicron to be attenuated even before its discovery. We also predicted that the
588 precursor would spread more slowly than SARS-CoV-2. This is still to be true
589 as we were assuming an M-PID of 5.9% or higher, unlike the Omicron M-PID
590 of 5.4%. While Omicron has a harder outer shell; i.e., it is more capable of
591 resisting the harsh nasal and mucosal enzymes, this may not be necessarily
592 true for the predicted SARS-CoV-2 precursor that is believed to be attenuated.
593 In fact, two of three known pangolin CoVs have M-PIDs, which are the same or
594 higher values than that of the Wuhan strain and Delta variant.

595 4.4. *How did it get to South Africa?*

596 As we are seeing, fast-spreading Omicron causes larger than previous
597 numbers of death, even being attenuated, because of the speed of the spread, as
598 a result of its harder outer shell. This may not have been the case for a SARS-
599 CoV-2 precursor, as it had silently and, perhaps, slowly but steadily spread in
600 humans for several years before it became more virulent. If it was a slow
601 moving and attenuated virus, doctors could have easily mistake it for a cold.
602 While scientists have pinpointed the Wuhan Seafood market as the epicenter of
603 an index case [97], this index case may have been a reflection of the initial virus
604 mutation into a more virulent form, not that it was the index case of a first
605 human spread with an attenuated precursor that had happened several years
606 before 2019.

607 These considerations, too, may explain the enigma of how did Omicron
608 get to South Africa so early, assuming that it was hiding in some burrowing
609 animals in South Africa? One possible explanation is that by the time Omicron
610 has done a reverse zoonotic transfer back to animals, the precursor virus has
611 already silently spread to a large human population and has even spread
612 overseas and reached South Africa via air travel. South Africa has large
613 varieties of burrowing animals including African pangolins [89]. It is not
614 difficult to imagine a scenario, where the virus can re-enter the animal
615 population through human activities. For instance, an infected person could
616 dispose his feces as trash along with sugary foods that attract ants, which then
617 in turn attract pangolins, and the pangolins eventually eat the ants along with
618 the virus-contaminated feces. This hypothesis is also supported by the
619 phylogenetic tree using M, which reveals that the Omicron did not originate
620 from the Wuhan strain but, rather, from one of its ancestors that has a closer
621 relationship to pangolin CoVs (Figure 4C). The reliability of this tree is
622 supported by the evolutionarily conserved nature of the M, which involves
623 transmission via buried feces, and the fact that current phylogenetic algorithms
624 handle recombination very poorly [88].

625 4.5. *Shell disorder predictions are consistent with incoming experimental and clinical 626 data pertaining to Omicron*

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628 The SDMs present a unique explanation for the Omicron attenuation,
629 which has been confirmed clinically. Omicron is mild because its N protein is
630 less disordered and therefore is unable to assist the virus more effectively in

631 the “Trojan Horse” immune evasion strategy, in which the virus tries to
632 replicate rapidly before the host immune system could detect its presence. As a
633 result, lesser numbers of viral particles are produced in vital organs such as the
634 lungs. On the other hand, heavier oral and nasal shedding also occur because
635 of the Omicron's harder outer shell that is more able to resist the anti-microbial
636 enzymes found in the mucus and saliva. This mechanism is actually being
637 supported by experimental studies throughout the world. An example is the
638 study made by Hong Kong University (HKU) that involves the separate
639 collections of tissues from the bronchi and lungs [35]. The tissues were then
640 infected with Omicron, variant Delta variant and Wuhan strain, and the
641 amounts of infectious particles present were studied and quantified. The
642 bronchial tissues infected with Omicron were found to have 70-times more
643 viral particles of the bronchial tissues infected with the Delta or the original
644 variant, whereas the lung tissues infected with Omicron had 10-times less viral
645 particles than the ones infected with the Wuhan virus. This is consistent with
646 what the predictions made by SDMs, since the walls of the bronchi and
647 bronchial cells are lined with a layer of mucus, unlike the lung aveoli. Similar
648 results have been obtained using mice and hamsters as animal models, and,
649 again [34], they do not contradict to what the SDMs have been saying. There is
650 also evidence that the layers of mucus in the bronchi act as a transport vehicle
651 that moves foreign matters away from the lungs, which could ultimately
652 increase that concentration of viral particles at the nasal cavity.

653 *4.6. N and M Disorder correlates with viral titers of SARS-CoV-2 in lungs and* 654 *bronchi*

655 If we look closer at the data coming from HKU [35], something else
656 intriguing can be seen. Upon 48 hours after infecting the lung tissue, tissues
657 infected with the Omicron variant, Delta variant, and Wuhan virus had the
658 viral titers of 1×10^3 , 3×10^3 , and 9×10^3 TCID₅₀ per ml (the Median Tissue
659 Culture Infectious Dose, which is defined as the dilution of a virus required to
660 infect 50% of a given cell culture). These were positively correlated ($r=0.88$, p
661 $=0.11$, poor p-value is due to small sample size, which is inevitable in this case)
662 with the N-PIDs of 44.8%, 47.1±0.6%, and 48.2%, respectively (**Tables 1-2**).
663 Infected bronchial tissues yielded even more interesting results. These tissues
664 infected with the Omicron variant, Delta variant, and Wuhan strain yielded
665 viral titers of 6×10^4 , 1×10^4 , and 1×10^3 TCID₅₀ per ml. While the yield from the
666 Omicron and Wuhan infections can be explained with the hardness of the M
667 (outer-shell) of 5.4% and 5.9%, the Delta is a puzzle since it has the same M-PID
668 as the Wuhan strain. One answer has something to do with the hardness of the
669 inner shell, N. We need to remember that the Delta variant has slightly lower
670 N-PID of 47.1±0.6% than the Wuhan N-PID of 48.2% (strong negative
671 correlation of bronchial viral titer to N- and M-PIDs ($r=0.99$, $p=0.07$, poor p-
672 value is due to small sample size). This basically implies that the inner shell
673 also plays some role in protecting the virion, namely the RNA, from damaging
674 effects of the anti-microbial enzymes found in the mucus.
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676 *4.7. Negative correlation of viral titer with shell disorder in the bronchi, not lungs:* 677 *Mucus network in bronchi, not lung aveoli*

678 An important question is: Why does the viral titer of infected lung tissue
679 positively correlate with the N disorder, whereas the viral titer of the infected
680 bronchial tissues have negative correlation with N and especially M disorder?
681 The answer is that there is a presence of mucus in walls and cells of the bronchi,
682 not found in the lung aveoli [98-99]. Not only does the mucus in the bronchi
683 have anti-microbial enzymes that could damage the virus [53-54], the mucus
684 network in the wall of the bronchi acts to transport viruses and other harmful
685 objects, that it is unable to destroy, away from the lungs[98-99]. The lungs, on
686 the other hand, can be divided into the conducting and respiratory zones [99].
687 The conducting zone includes the bronchioles that, as mentioned, use mucus to
688 transport foreign materials away from the lungs. More importantly, there is also
689 the respiratory zone that includes aveolar cells, which are not covered by
690 mucus but, rather by a surfactant [98] that also acts to remove foreign debris
691 away from the lungs. In other words, much of the lung is devoid of mucosal
692 anti-microbial enzymes, unlike the bronchi and bronchial cells. This is a highly
693 crucial factor that has unfortunately been totally overlooked in all current
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analyses of such experiments that have led to much misconception of the actual mechanism of viral infections involved. .

4.8. *New knowledge from SARS-CoV-2 and Omicron is strengthening our understanding of the Shell Disorder Models as applied to SARS-CoV-2*

We have actually seen the characteristics of both inner and outer shells protecting the virion from damage before in the case of the rabies virus [16,24,25] and the close retroviral relatives, HIV and EIAV [26,28]. HIV is predominantly sexually transmitted and does not have to be exposed to any harsh environment, whereas its horse cousin, EIAV, is transmitted by a blood-sucking horsefly that stores infected blood mixed with its saliva in its mouthpiece. It is therefore also not surprising that while HIV-1 has a high outer shell disorder (Matrix PID: 56.5 ± 10.8) and a moderately high inner shell disorder (Capsid PID: 44.6 ± 2.8 ; Nucleocapsid: 39.5 ± 3), EIAV has very low PIDs for all its shell proteins (Matrix PID: 13 ± 0.1 ; Capsid PID: 29 ± 0.1 ; Nucleocapsid PID: $26 \pm 0.1\%$). What is amazing is the fact that Omicron does not only reproduce what the SDMs are predicting again but also adds to our knowledge of the models. We also know now that pangolins provide evolutionary advantage for lower N-PID that protects the virus in the buried feces. This is an added reason to believe that Omicron may have been hiding in a burrowing animal like pangolin all these years. The burrowing animal provides an evolutionary ideal environment for lower N and M disorder.

5. Summary and Conclusions

While Omicron is currently shrouded with mysteries, the SDMs have specific answers to many of these mysteries that are linked to the peculiar evolution of SARS-CoV-2 in general, and not just Omicron. Prior to the discovery of Omicron in South Africa, the SDMs suggested that an attenuated precursor may have entered humans from pangolins in 2017 if not earlier, and that this precursor was spreading slower than the SARS-CoV-2 (Wuhan strain). This prediction was based on the lower N disorder levels (N-PID: 44.9%) with the assumption that the M remains the same or is higher than that of the Wuhan strain. When the fast moving but milder Omicron emerged, it turned out that the N of Omicron resembles pangolin CoV 2017 (N-PID: 44.8%), but this variant showed harder outer shell (M-PID: 5.4%). We were not surprised by the attenuation, but were surprised by the effects of a harder outer shell, even when we already knew that SARS-CoV-2 was more contagious than SARS-CoV-1 (M-PID: 9%), because of the much harder outer shell of SARS-CoV-2 (M-PID: 5.9%). SARS-CoV-1 is more virulent than SARS-CoV-2, as SARS-CoV-1 has a greater disorder at its inner shell protein (N-PID: 50%) compared to SARS-CoV-2 (Wuhan N-PID: 48.2%) since the Virulence-Inner Shell Disorder Model suggests that greater disorder at the inner shell helps faster replication of viral particles especially in vital organs. SARS-CoV-2., on the other hand, sheds greater numbers of infectious particles because its harder outer shell protects the virion from harsh environment and anti-microbial enzymes found orally and nasally.

This paradigm is consistent with the incoming data pertaining to Omicron. For instance, using incoming data from HKU, strong correlation is found between N-PID and viral titers of lung tissues infected with Omicron, Wuhan strain, and Delta, whereas, in the case of bronchial tissues, correlation is found between shell (N- and M-PID) hardness and viral titers. What is surprising is that Omicron and Delta indicate that both shells play roles in protecting the virion from damage. We have actually seen this characteristic in other viruses, such as EIAV. Nevertheless, Omicron has shown us that the outer shell hardness contributes the most towards the infectiousness of the disease. Once again, the COVID-19 pandemic is an event that is not only reproducing our predictions but also adding to our knowledge on how the SDMs should be applied more accurately to SARS-CoV-2 and perhaps, other viruses.

We have seen that the outer shell plays an important role in the spread of CoV in both humans and pangolins. The hard outer shell (low M-PID) allows greater contagiousness, whereas the low M disorder provides greater fitness in the fecal-oral-respiratory spread among burrowing animals, such as pangolins,

758 likely via buried feces. As a result, M-PIDs of all COVID-19-related CoVs are
759 among the lowest in the entire CoV family, which makes it ideal for the
760 phylogenetic study as it is evolutionarily conserved. Indeed, the phylogenetic
761 tree using M has uncovered many things not seen before. It revealed that
762 Omicron spilt off not from the Wuhan strain but, rather, from one of its
763 ancestors that is closer to the pangolin CoVs. This raises many questions. We
764 have already addressed some of them. A previous phylogenetic study using S1
765 mentioned that Omicron broke off from the Wuhan strain a few months after
766 the first outbreak that began at the end of 2019. We believe that such studies
767 have been misled by the high probability that Omicron had acquired bits and
768 pieces of proteins from other variants when it re-emerged from a burrowing
769 animals back to humans. Current phylogenetic algorithms do not handle
770 recombination well [88]. The SDMs also suggest that Omicron had been hiding
771 among a specie of burrowing animals like pangolins through reverse zoonotic
772 transfer back to animals as burrowing animals would provide the necessary
773 evolutionary environment for the virus to retain its attenuation and, yet,
774 increase the hardness of its outer shell as a result of the behaviors of such
775 animals via exposure to buried feces. The Omicron data add important
776 evidence to the suggestion that an attenuated SARS-CoV-2 precursor entered
777 humans in 2017 or before from pangolin-CoVs.

778
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799 References

- 800 1. WHO. Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) pandemic. Availabe online:
801 <https://www.who.int/emergencies/diseases/novel-coronavirus-2019> (accessed on February 24, 2022).
- 802 2. Hu, B.; Guo, H.; Zhou, P.; Shi, Z.L. Characteristics of SARS-CoV-2 and COVID-19. *Nat Rev Microbiol* **2021**, *19*,
803 141-154, doi:10.1038/s41579-020-00459-7.
- 804 3. Abraham, T. *Twenty-first century plague: the story of SARS*; JHU Press: 2007.
- 805 4. Zhou, P.; Yang, X.L.; Wang, X.G.; Hu, B.; Zhang, L.; Zhang, W.; Si, H.R.; Zhu, Y.; Li, B.; Huang, C.L., et al.
806 Addendum: A pneumonia outbreak associated with a new coronavirus of probable bat origin. *Nature* **2020**, *588*,
807 E6, doi:10.1038/s41586-020-2951-z.
- 808 5. Li, X.; Zai, J.; Zhao, Q.; Nie, Q.; Li, Y.; Foley, B.T.; Chaillon, A. Evolutionary history, potential intermediate
809 animal host, and cross-species analyses of SARS-CoV-2. *J Med Virol* **2020**, *92*, 602-611, doi:10.1002/jmv.25731.
- 810 6. Zhou, P.; Yang, X.L.; Wang, X.G.; Hu, B.; Zhang, L.; Zhang, W.; Si, H.R.; Zhu, Y.; Li, B.; Huang, C.L., et al. A
811 pneumonia outbreak associated with a new coronavirus of probable bat origin. *Nature* **2020**, *579*, 270-273,
812 doi:10.1038/s41586-020-2012-7.
- 813 7. Fan, H.-H.; Wang, L.-Q.; Liu, W.-L.; An, X.-P.; Liu, Z.-D.; He, X.-Q.; Song, L.-H.; Tong, Y.-G. Repurposing of
814 clinically approved drugs for treatment of coronavirus disease 2019 in a 2019-novel coronavirus-related
815 coronavirus model. *Chinese medical journal* **2020**, *133*, 1051-1056.
- 816 8. Low, Z.Y.; Yip, A.J.W.; Sharma, A.; Lal, S.K. SARS coronavirus outbreaks past and present—a comparative
817 analysis of SARS-CoV-2 and its predecessors. *Virus Genes* **2021**, *57*, 307-317, doi:10.1007/s11262-021-01846-9.

- 818 9. Xiao, K.; Zhai, J.; Feng, Y.; Zhou, N.; Zhang, X.; Zou, J.J.; Li, N.; Guo, Y.; Li, X.; Shen, X., et al. Isolation of SARS-
819 CoV-2-related coronavirus from Malayan pangolins. *Nature* **2020**, *583*, 286-289, doi:10.1038/s41586-020-2313-x.
- 820 10. Lam, T.T.; Jia, N.; Zhang, Y.W.; Shum, M.H.; Jiang, J.F.; Zhu, H.C.; Tong, Y.G.; Shi, Y.X.; Ni, X.B.; Liao, Y.S., et al.
821 Identifying SARS-CoV-2-related coronaviruses in Malayan pangolins. *Nature* **2020**, *583*, 282-285,
822 doi:10.1038/s41586-020-2169-0.
- 823 11. Zhang, T.; Wu, Q.; Zhang, Z. Probable Pangolin Origin of SARS-CoV-2 Associated with the COVID-19
824 Outbreak. *Curr Biol* **2020**, *30*, 1346-1351 e1342, doi:10.1016/j.cub.2020.03.022.
- 825 12. CDC. SARS-CoV-2 variant classification and definitions. Available online:
826 <https://www.cdc.gov/coronavirus/2019-ncov/variants/variant-classifications.html> (accessed on February 24).
- 827 13. Abdullah, F.; Myers, J.; Basu, D.; Tintinger, G.; Ueckermann, V.; Mathebula, M.; Ramlall, R.; Spoor, S.; de
828 Villiers, T.; Van der Walt, Z., et al. Decreased severity of disease during the first global omicron variant covid-19
829 outbreak in a large hospital in tshwane, south africa. *Int J Infect Dis* **2022**, *116*, 38-42,
830 doi:10.1016/j.ijid.2021.12.357.
- 831 14. Wolter, N.; Jassat, W.; Walaza, S.; Welch, R.; Moultrie, H.; Groome, M.; Amoako, D.G.; Everatt, J.; Bhiman, J.N.;
832 Scheepers, C. Early assessment of the clinical severity of the SARS-CoV-2 Omicron variant in South Africa.
833 *Medrxiv* **2021**.
- 834 15. Kupferschmidt, K. Where did 'weird' Omicron come from? *Science* **2021**, *374*, 1179, doi:10.1126/science.acx9738.
- 835 16. Goh, G.K. *Viral Shapeshifters: Strange Behaviors of HIV and Other Viruses*; Simplicity Research Institute: 2017.
- 836 17. Goh, G.K.; Dunker, A.K.; Foster, J.A.; Uversky, V.N. Shell Disorder Analysis Suggests That Pangolins Offered a
837 Window for a Silent Spread of an Attenuated SARS-CoV-2 Precursor among Humans. *J Proteome Res* **2020**, *19*,
838 4543-4552, doi:10.1021/acs.jproteome.0c00460.
- 839 18. Goh, G.K.; Dunker, A.K.; Foster, J.A.; Uversky, V.N. Computational, Experimental, and Clinical Evidence of a
840 Specific but Peculiar Evolutionary Nature of (COVID-19) SARS-CoV-2. *J Proteome Res* **2022**,
841 10.1021/acs.jproteome.2c00001, doi:10.1021/acs.jproteome.2c00001.
- 842 19. Goh, G.K.; Dunker, A.K.; Foster, J.A.; Uversky, V.N. Nipah shell disorder, modes of infection, and virulence.
843 *Microb Pathog* **2020**, *141*, 103976, doi:10.1016/j.micpath.2020.103976.
- 844 20. Goh, G.K.; Dunker, A.K.; Foster, J.A.; Uversky, V.N. Zika and Flavivirus Shell Disorder: Virulence and Fetal
845 Morbidity. *Biomolecules* **2019**, *9*, doi:10.3390/biom9110710.
- 846 21. Goh, G.K.; Dunker, A.K.; Uversky, V.N. Correlating Flavivirus virulence and levels of intrinsic disorder in shell
847 proteins: protective roles vs. immune evasion. *Mol Biosyst* **2016**, *12*, 1881-1891, doi:10.1039/c6mb00228e.
- 848 22. Goh, G.K.; Dunker, A.K.; Uversky, V.N. Detection of links between Ebola nucleocapsid and virulence using
849 disorder analysis. *Mol Biosyst* **2015**, *11*, 2337-2344, doi:10.1039/c5mb00240k.
- 850 23. Goh, G.K.; Dunker, A.K.; Uversky, V.N. Understanding Viral Transmission Behavior via Protein Intrinsic
851 Disorder Prediction: Coronaviruses. *J Pathog* **2012**, *2012*, 738590, doi:10.1155/2012/738590.
- 852 24. Goh, G.K.; Dunker, A.K.; Uversky, V.N. A comparative analysis of viral matrix proteins using disorder
853 predictors. *Virol J* **2008**, *5*, 126, doi:10.1186/1743-422X-5-126.
- 854 25. Goh, G.K.; Dunker, A.K.; Uversky, V.N. Protein intrinsic disorder toolbox for comparative analysis of viral
855 proteins. *BMC Genomics* **2008**, *9 Suppl 2*, S4, doi:10.1186/1471-2164-9-S2-S4.
- 856 26. Goh, G.K.; Dunker, A.K.; Foster, J.A.; Uversky, V.N. HIV Vaccine Mystery and Viral Shell Disorder. *Biomolecules*
857 **2019**, *9*, doi:10.3390/biom9050178.
- 858 27. Goh, G.K.; Dunker, A.K.; Foster, J.A.; Uversky, V.N. Feasibility of the vaccine development for SARS-CoV-2 and
859 other viruses using the shell disorder analysis. *Pac Symp Biocomput* **2021**, *26*, 143-153.
- 860 28. Goh, G.K.; Uversky, V.N. Shell disorder and the HIV vaccine mystery: lessons from the legendary Oswald
861 Avery. *J Biomol Struct Dyn* **2021**, 10.1080/07391102.2020.1870562, 1-10, doi:10.1080/07391102.2020.1870562.
- 862 29. Garner, E.; Romero, P.; Dunker, A.K.; Brown, C.; Obradovic, Z. Predicting Binding Regions within Disordered
863 Proteins. *Genome Inform Ser Workshop Genome Inform* **1999**, *10*, 41-50.
- 864 30. Romero, P.; Obradovic, Z.; Li, X.; Garner, E.C.; Brown, C.J.; Dunker, A.K. Sequence complexity of disordered
865 protein. *Proteins* **2001**, *42*, 38-48, doi:10.1002/1097-0134(20010101)42:1<38::aid-prot50>3.0.co;2-3.
- 866 31. Li, X.; Romero, P.; Rani, M.; Dunker, A.K.; Obradovic, Z. Predicting Protein Disorder for N-, C-, and Internal
867 Regions. *Genome Inform Ser Workshop Genome Inform* **1999**, *10*, 30-40.
- 868 32. Garner, E.; Cannon, P.; Romero, P.; Obradovic, Z.; Dunker, A.K. Predicting Disordered Regions from Amino
869 Acid Sequence: Common Themes Despite Differing Structural Characterization. *Genome Inform Ser Workshop
870 Genome Inform* **1998**, *9*, 201-213.
- 871 33. Goh, G.K.; Dunker, A.K.; Foster, J.A.; Uversky, V.N. Shell disorder analysis predicts greater resilience of the
872 SARS-CoV-2 (COVID-19) outside the body and in body fluids. *Microb Pathog* **2020**, *144*, 104177,
873 doi:10.1016/j.micpath.2020.104177.

- 874 34. Diamond, M.; Halfmann, P.; Maemura, T.; Iwatsuki-Horimoto, K.; Iida, S.; Kiso, M.; Scheaffer, S.; Darling, T.;
875 Joshi, A.; Loeber, S., et al. The SARS-CoV-2 B.1.1.529 Omicron virus causes attenuated infection and disease in
876 mice and hamsters. *Res Sq* **2021**, 10.21203/rs.3.rs-1211792/v1, doi:10.21203/rs.3.rs-1211792/v1.
- 877 35. HKU. HKUMed finds Omicron SARS-CoV-2 can infect faster and better than Delta in human bronchus but with
878 less severe infection in lung. Available online: [https://www.med.hku.hk/en/news/press/20211215-omicron-](https://www.med.hku.hk/en/news/press/20211215-omicron-sars-cov-2-infection)
879 [sars-cov-2-infection](https://www.med.hku.hk/en/news/press/20211215-omicron-sars-cov-2-infection) (accessed on February 24).
- 880 36. Wright, P.E.; Dyson, H.J. Intrinsically unstructured proteins: re-assessing the protein structure-function
881 paradigm. *J Mol Biol* **1999**, 293, 321-331, doi:10.1006/jmbi.1999.3110.
- 882 37. Uversky, V.N.; Gillespie, J.R.; Fink, A.L. Why are "natively unfolded" proteins unstructured under physiologic
883 conditions? *Proteins* **2000**, 41, 415-427, doi:10.1002/1097-0134(20001115)41:3<415::aid-prot130>3.0.co;2-7.
- 884 38. Dunker, A.K.; Lawson, J.D.; Brown, C.J.; Williams, R.M.; Romero, P.; Oh, J.S.; Oldfield, C.J.; Campen, A.M.;
885 Ratliff, C.M.; Hipps, K.W., et al. Intrinsically disordered protein. *J Mol Graph Model* **2001**, 19, 26-59,
886 doi:10.1016/s1093-3263(00)00138-8.
- 887 39. Dunker, A.K.; Brown, C.J.; Lawson, J.D.; Iakoucheva, L.M.; Obradovic, Z. Intrinsic disorder and protein
888 function. *Biochemistry* **2002**, 41, 6573-6582, doi:10.1021/bi012159+.
- 889 40. Tompa, P. Intrinsically unstructured proteins. *Trends Biochem Sci* **2002**, 27, 527-533, doi:10.1016/s0968-
890 0004(02)02169-2.
- 891 41. Uversky, V.N. Natively unfolded proteins: a point where biology waits for physics. *Protein Sci* **2002**, 11, 739-756,
892 doi:10.1110/ps.4210102.
- 893 42. Uversky, V.N. What does it mean to be natively unfolded? *Eur J Biochem* **2002**, 269, 2-12, doi:10.1046/j.0014-
894 2956.2001.02649.x.
- 895 43. Oldfield, C.J.; Cheng, Y.; Cortese, M.S.; Romero, P.; Uversky, V.N.; Dunker, A.K. Coupled folding and binding
896 with alpha-helix-forming molecular recognition elements. *Biochemistry* **2005**, 44, 12454-12470,
897 doi:10.1021/bi050736e.
- 898 44. Cheng, Y.; Oldfield, C.J.; Meng, J.; Romero, P.; Uversky, V.N.; Dunker, A.K. Mining alpha-helix-forming
899 molecular recognition features with cross species sequence alignments. *Biochemistry* **2007**, 46, 13468-13477,
900 doi:10.1021/bi7012273.
- 901 45. Goh, G.K.; Dunker, A.K.; Uversky, V.N. Protein intrinsic disorder and influenza virulence: the 1918 H1N1 and
902 H5N1 viruses. *Virol J* **2009**, 6, 69, doi:10.1186/1743-422X-6-69.
- 903 46. Goh, G.K.; Dunker, A.K.; Uversky, V. Prediction of Intrinsic Disorder in MERS-CoV/HCoV-EMC Supports a
904 High Oral-Fecal Transmission. *PLoS Curr* **2013**, 5,
905 doi:10.1371/currents.outbreaks.22254b58675cdebc256dbe3c5aa6498b.
- 906 47. Goh, G.K.; Dunker, A.K.; Foster, J.A.; Uversky, V.N. A Novel Strategy for the Development of Vaccines for
907 SARS-CoV-2 (COVID-19) and Other Viruses Using AI and Viral Shell Disorder. *J Proteome Res* **2020**, 19, 4355-
908 4363, doi:10.1021/acs.jproteome.0c00672.
- 909 48. Goh, G.K.; Dunker, A.K.; Foster, J.A.; Uversky, V.N. Rigidity of the Outer Shell Predicted by a Protein Intrinsic
910 Disorder Model Sheds Light on the COVID-19 (Wuhan-2019-nCoV) Infectivity. *Biomolecules* **2020**, 10,
911 doi:10.3390/biom10020331.
- 912 49. R_Core_Team. R: A language and environment for statistical computing; Vienna, Austria. **2013**.
- 913 50. Woo, P.C.; Lau, S.K.; Chu, C.M.; Chan, K.H.; Tsoi, H.W.; Huang, Y.; Wong, B.H.; Poon, R.W.; Cai, J.J.; Luk, W.K.,
914 et al. Characterization and complete genome sequence of a novel coronavirus, coronavirus HKU1, from patients
915 with pneumonia. *J Virol* **2005**, 79, 884-895, doi:10.1128/JVI.79.2.884-895.2005.
- 916 51. Liu, P.-L.; Shi, L.; Gu, D.-Y. Progress in researches on human coronavirus HKU1: A review. *Chinese Journal of*
917 *Public Health* **2017**, 33, 1264-1266, doi:10.11847/zgggws2017-33-08-27.
- 918 52. Longhi, S.; Oglesbee, M. Structural disorder within the measles virus nucleoprotein and phosphoprotein.
919 *Protein Pept Lett* **2010**, 17, 961-978, doi:10.2174/092986610791498894.
- 920 53. Cole, A.M.; Dewan, P.; Ganz, T. Innate antimicrobial activity of nasal secretions. *Infect Immun* **1999**, 67, 3267-
921 3275, doi:10.1128/IAI.67.7.3267-3275.1999.
- 922 54. Malamud, D.; Abrams, W.R.; Barber, C.A.; Weissman, D.; Rehtanz, M.; Golub, E. Antiviral activities in human
923 saliva. *Adv Dent Res* **2011**, 23, 34-37, doi:10.1177/0022034511399282.
- 924 55. Uversky, V.N.; Roman, A.; Oldfield, C.J.; Dunker, A.K. Protein intrinsic disorder and human papillomaviruses:
925 increased amount of disorder in E6 and E7 oncoproteins from high risk HPVs. *J Proteome Res* **2006**, 5, 1829-1842,
926 doi:10.1021/pr0602388.
- 927 56. Xue, B.; Williams, R.W.; Oldfield, C.J.; Goh, G.K.; Dunker, A.K.; Uversky, V.N. Viral disorder or disordered
928 viruses: do viral proteins possess unique features? *Protein Pept Lett* **2010**, 17, 932-951,
929 doi:10.2174/092986610791498984.

- 930 57. Xue, B.; Dunker, A.K.; Uversky, V.N. Orderly order in protein intrinsic disorder distribution: disorder in 3500
931 proteomes from viruses and the three domains of life. *J Biomol Struct Dyn* **2012**, *30*, 137-149,
932 doi:10.1080/07391102.2012.675145.
- 933 58. Xue, B.; Mizianty, M.J.; Kurgan, L.; Uversky, V.N. Protein intrinsic disorder as a flexible armor and a weapon of
934 HIV-1. *Cell Mol Life Sci* **2012**, *69*, 1211-1259, doi:10.1007/s00018-011-0859-3.
- 935 59. Fan, X.; Xue, B.; Dolan, P.T.; LaCount, D.J.; Kurgan, L.; Uversky, V.N. The intrinsic disorder status of the human
936 hepatitis C virus proteome. *Mol Biosyst* **2014**, *10*, 1345-1363, doi:10.1039/c4mb00027g.
- 937 60. Xue, B.; Blocquel, D.; Habchi, J.; Uversky, A.V.; Kurgan, L.; Uversky, V.N.; Longhi, S. Structural disorder in viral
938 proteins. *Chem Rev* **2014**, *114*, 6880-6911, doi:10.1021/cr4005692.
- 939 61. Xue, B.; Ganti, K.; Rabionet, A.; Banks, L.; Uversky, V.N. Disordered interactome of human papillomavirus.
940 *Curr Pharm Des* **2014**, *20*, 1274-1292, doi:10.2174/13816128113199990072.
- 941 62. Dolan, P.T.; Roth, A.P.; Xue, B.; Sun, R.; Dunker, A.K.; Uversky, V.N.; LaCount, D.J. Intrinsic disorder mediates
942 hepatitis C virus core-host cell protein interactions. *Protein Sci* **2015**, *24*, 221-235, doi:10.1002/pro.2608.
- 943 63. Meng, F.; Badierah, R.A.; Almehdar, H.A.; Redwan, E.M.; Kurgan, L.; Uversky, V.N. Unstructural biology of the
944 Dengue virus proteins. *FEBS J* **2015**, *282*, 3368-3394, doi:10.1111/febs.13349.
- 945 64. Peng, Z.; Yan, J.; Fan, X.; Mizianty, M.J.; Xue, B.; Wang, K.; Hu, G.; Uversky, V.N.; Kurgan, L. Exceptionally
946 abundant exceptions: comprehensive characterization of intrinsic disorder in all domains of life. *Cell Mol Life Sci*
947 **2015**, *72*, 137-151, doi:10.1007/s00018-014-1661-9.
- 948 65. Giri, R.; Kumar, D.; Sharma, N.; Uversky, V.N. Intrinsically Disordered Side of the Zika Virus Proteome. *Front*
949 *Cell Infect Microbiol* **2016**, *6*, 144, doi:10.3389/fcimb.2016.00144.
- 950 66. Whelan, J.N.; Reddy, K.D.; Uversky, V.N.; Teng, M.N. Functional correlations of respiratory syncytial virus
951 proteins to intrinsic disorder. *Mol Biosyst* **2016**, *12*, 1507-1526, doi:10.1039/c6mb00122j.
- 952 67. Mishra, P.M.; Uversky, V.N.; Giri, R. Molecular Recognition Features in Zika Virus Proteome. *J Mol Biol* **2018**,
953 *430*, 2372-2388, doi:10.1016/j.jmb.2017.10.018.
- 954 68. Singh, A.; Kumar, A.; Yadav, R.; Uversky, V.N.; Giri, R. Deciphering the dark proteome of Chikungunya virus.
955 *Sci Rep* **2018**, *8*, 5822, doi:10.1038/s41598-018-23969-0.
- 956 69. Redwan, E.M.; AlJaddawi, A.A.; Uversky, V.N. Structural disorder in the proteome and interactome of
957 Alkhurma virus (ALKV). *Cell Mol Life Sci* **2019**, *76*, 577-608, doi:10.1007/s00018-018-2968-8.
- 958 70. Bhardwaj, T.; Saumya, K.U.; Kumar, P.; Sharma, N.; Gadhav, K.; Uversky, V.N.; Giri, R. Japanese encephalitis
959 virus - exploring the dark proteome and disorder-function paradigm. *FEBS J* **2020**, *287*, 3751-3776,
960 doi:10.1111/febs.15427.
- 961 71. Kumar, D.; Singh, A.; Kumar, P.; Uversky, V.N.; Rao, C.D.; Giri, R. Understanding the penetrance of intrinsic
962 protein disorder in rotavirus proteome. *Int J Biol Macromol* **2020**, *144*, 892-908,
963 doi:10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2019.09.166.
- 964 72. Mishra, P.M.; Verma, N.C.; Rao, C.; Uversky, V.N.; Nandi, C.K. Intrinsically disordered proteins of viruses:
965 Involvement in the mechanism of cell regulation and pathogenesis. *Prog Mol Biol Transl Sci* **2020**, *174*, 1-78,
966 doi:10.1016/bs.pmbts.2020.03.001.
- 967 73. Alshehri, M.A.; Manee, M.M.; Alqahtani, F.H.; Al-Shomrani, B.M.; Uversky, V.N. On the Prevalence and
968 Potential Functionality of an Intrinsic Disorder in the MERS-CoV Proteome. *Viruses* **2021**, *13*,
969 doi:10.3390/v13020339.
- 970 74. Giri, R.; Bhardwaj, T.; Shegane, M.; Gehi, B.R.; Kumar, P.; Gadhav, K.; Oldfield, C.J.; Uversky, V.N.
971 Understanding COVID-19 via comparative analysis of dark proteomes of SARS-CoV-2, human SARS and bat
972 SARS-like coronaviruses. *Cell Mol Life Sci* **2021**, *78*, 1655-1688, doi:10.1007/s00018-020-03603-x.
- 973 75. Kumar, N.; Kaushik, R.; Tennakoon, C.; Uversky, V.N.; Longhi, S.; Zhang, K.Y.J.; Bhatia, S. Comprehensive
974 Intrinsic Disorder Analysis of 6108 Viral Proteomes: From the Extent of Intrinsic Disorder Penetrance to
975 Functional Annotation of Disordered Viral Proteins. *J Proteome Res* **2021**, *20*, 2704-2713,
976 doi:10.1021/acs.jproteome.1c00011.
- 977 76. Sen, S.; Dey, A.; Bandhyopadhyay, S.; Uversky, V.N.; Maulik, U. Understanding structural malleability of the
978 SARS-CoV-2 proteins and relation to the comorbidities. *Brief Bioinform* **2021**, *22*, doi:10.1093/bib/bbab232.
- 979 77. Sharma, N.R.; Gadhav, K.; Kumar, P.; Saif, M.; Khan, M.M.; Sarkar, D.P.; Uversky, V.N.; Giri, R. Analysis of the
980 dark proteome of Chandipura virus reveals maximum propensity for intrinsic disorder in phosphoprotein. *Sci*
981 *Rep* **2021**, *11*, 13253, doi:10.1038/s41598-021-92581-6.
- 982 78. Uversky, V.N.; Redwan, E.M.; Aljadawi, A.A. Protein Intrinsic Disorder and Evolvability of MERS-CoV.
983 *Biomolecules* **2021**, *11*, doi:10.3390/biom11040608.
- 984 79. Badierah, R.A.; Uversky, V.N.; Redwan, E.M. Dancing with Trojan horses: an interplay between the
985 extracellular vesicles and viruses. *J Biomol Struct Dyn* **2021**, *39*, 3034-3060, doi:10.1080/07391102.2020.1756409.

- 986 80. Rajgor, D.D.; Lee, M.H.; Archuleta, S.; Bagdasarian, N.; Quek, S.C. The many estimates of the COVID-19 case
987 fatality rate. *Lancet Infect Dis* **2020**, *20*, 776-777, doi:10.1016/S1473-3099(20)30244-9.
- 988 81. European_CDC. European Center for Disease Prevention and Control, Weekly epidemiological update: Omicron
989 variant of concern (VOC). Available online: [https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/news-events/weekly-
990 epidemiological-update-omicron-variant-concern-voc-week-2-data-20-january-2022](https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/news-events/weekly-epidemiological-update-omicron-variant-concern-voc-week-2-data-20-january-2022) (accessed on February 24).
- 991 82. McBride, R.; Van Zyl, M.; Fielding, B.C. The Coronavirus Nucleocapsid Is a Multifunctional Protein. *Viruses*
992 **2014**, *6*, 2991-3018.
- 993 83. Radivojac, P.; Iakoucheva, L.M.; Oldfield, C.J.; Obradovic, Z.; Uversky, V.N.; Dunker, A.K. Intrinsic disorder
994 and functional proteomics. *Biophys J* **2007**, *92*, 1439-1456, doi:10.1529/biophysj.106.094045.
- 995 84. Uversky, V.N.; Radivojac, P.; Iakoucheva, L.M.; Obradovic, Z.; Dunker, A.K. Prediction of intrinsic disorder and
996 its use in functional proteomics. *Methods Mol Biol* **2007**, *408*, 69-92, doi:10.1007/978-1-59745-547-3_5.
- 997 85. Vacic, V.; Uversky, V.N.; Dunker, A.K.; Lonardi, S. Composition Profiler: a tool for discovery and visualization
998 of amino acid composition differences. *BMC Bioinformatics* **2007**, *8*, 211, doi:10.1186/1471-2105-8-211.
- 999 86. Vacic, V.; Iakoucheva, L.M. Disease mutations in disordered regions--exception to the rule? *Mol Biosyst* **2012**, *8*,
1000 27-32, doi:10.1039/c1mb05251a.
- 1001 87. Vacic, V.; Markwick, P.R.; Oldfield, C.J.; Zhao, X.; Haynes, C.; Uversky, V.N.; Iakoucheva, L.M. Disease-
1002 associated mutations disrupt functionally important regions of intrinsic protein disorder. *PLoS Comput Biol*
1003 **2012**, *8*, e1002709, doi:10.1371/journal.pcbi.1002709.
- 1004 88. Posada, D. How does recombination affect phylogeny estimation? *Trends Ecol Evol* **2000**, *15*, 489-490,
1005 doi:10.1016/s0169-5347(00)02027-9.
- 1006 89. Lehmann, D.; Halbwax, M.L.; Makaga, L.; Whytock, R.; Ndindiwe Malata, L.L.; Bombenda Mouele, W.;
1007 Momboua, B.R.; Koumba Pambo, A.F.; White, L.J.T. Pangolins and bats living together in underground
1008 burrows in Lope National Park, Gabon. *Afr J Ecol* **2020**, 10.1111/aje.12759, doi:10.1111/aje.12759.
- 1009 90. Andersen, K.G.; Rambaut, A.; Lipkin, W.I.; Holmes, E.C.; Garry, R.F. The proximal origin of SARS-CoV-2. *Nat*
1010 *Med* **2020**, *26*, 450-452, doi:10.1038/s41591-020-0820-9.
- 1011 91. Ogando, N.S.; Dalebout, T.J.; Zevenhoven-Dobbe, J.C.; Limpens, R.; van der Meer, Y.; Caly, L.; Druce, J.; de
1012 Vries, J.J.C.; Kikkert, M.; Barcena, M., et al. SARS-coronavirus-2 replication in Vero E6 cells: replication kinetics,
1013 rapid adaptation and cytopathology. *J Gen Virol* **2020**, *101*, 925-940, doi:10.1099/jgv.0.001453.
- 1014 92. Wolfel, R.; Corman, V.M.; Guggemos, W.; Seilmaier, M.; Zange, S.; Muller, M.A.; Niemeyer, D.; Jones, T.C.;
1015 Vollmar, P.; Rothe, C., et al. Virological assessment of hospitalized patients with COVID-2019. *Nature* **2020**, *581*,
1016 465-469, doi:10.1038/s41586-020-2196-x.
- 1017 93. Mahase, E. Covid-19: Past infection provides 83% protection for five months but may not stop transmission,
1018 study finds. *BMJ* **2021**, *372*, n124, doi:10.1136/bmj.n124.
- 1019 94. Choi, B.; Choudhary, M.C.; Regan, J.; Sparks, J.A.; Padera, R.F.; Qiu, X.; Solomon, I.H.; Kuo, H.H.; Boucau, J.;
1020 Bowman, K., et al. Persistence and Evolution of SARS-CoV-2 in an Immunocompromised Host. *N Engl J Med*
1021 **2020**, *383*, 2291-2293, doi:10.1056/NEJMc2031364.
- 1022 95. Wei, C.; Shan, K.J.; Wang, W.; Zhang, S.; Huan, Q.; Qian, W. Evidence for a mouse origin of the SARS-CoV-2
1023 Omicron variant. *J Genet Genomics* **2021**, *48*, 1111-1121, doi:10.1016/j.jgg.2021.12.003.
- 1024 96. Schmid-Holmes, S.; Drickamer, L.C.; Robinson, A.S.; Gillie, L.L. Burrows and burrow-cleaning behavior of
1025 house mice (*Mus musculus domesticus*). *The American Midland Naturalist* **2001**, *146*, 53-62.
- 1026 97. Worobey, M. Dissecting the early COVID-19 cases in Wuhan. *Science* **2021**, *374*, 1202-1204,
1027 doi:10.1126/science.abm4454.
- 1028 98. Fahy, J.B.; Dickey, B.F. Airways mucus function and disfunction. *New Eng. J. Med.* **2010**, *363*, 2233-2247,
1029 doi: [10.1056/NEJMra0910061](https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMra0910061)
- 1030 99. Weupe, M.; et al. Moving mucus matters for lung health. *Font. Young Minds* **2019**, *7*, 16,6,
1031 doi: 10.3389/frym.2019.00106
- 1032